

POLITENESS IN THE LITERARY WORKS: THE ARTISTIC PICTURE OF THE WORLD AS A MANIFESTATION OF ARTISTIC THINKING

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Fiction is a creative and individual knowledge of the world transmitted to the reader through language. It is a repository of cultural values and individual author's views and ideas. The language of fiction is a way of verbalizing thinking. According to O.G. Revzina, "poetic language extracts the hidden knowledge about the world contained in language." The existence of artistic thinking as a certain way of extracting knowledge is beyond doubt. It is "artistic" knowledge as an aesthetic way of cognition of the world, the sensual exploration of reality.

Fiction creates an artistic picture of the world, which is distinguished within the framework of the linguistic picture of the world [1,5]. An artistic picture of the world is an image of the world in the aesthetic point of view, an integral category of artistic creativity, which is also called an internal individual model of the world [2,36], as well as a nominal model of the world [3,12].

Researchers define an artistic picture of the world as "a secondary picture of the world, similar to a linguistic one, arising in the reader's mind when his perception of the work of art. The picture of the world in a literary text is created by linguistic means, while it reflects the individual picture of the world in the writer's mind and is embodied in the selection of elements of the content of the work of art, the selection of the language means used, in the individual use of figurative means. In the artistic picture of the world, concepts inherent only in this author's perception of the world, individual concepts of the writer can be found"[4,19]. The artistic picture of the writer's world reflects both individual the author's concepts underlying his work, as well as collective, national and universal concepts. That is why creativity is also a way of comprehending objective reality at a deep level and with a high degree of generalization and abstraction.

The artistic picture of the world and artistic thinking are closely related to the mentality and the conceptual sphere. The concepts of "mentality" and "the result of mentality" are differentiated in sociology and psychology. In social psychology, "mentality" is defined as the unconscious or semi-

conscious nature of mental life caused by factors and living conditions. "Mentality" is understood as the result of mentality and is put on a higher level. It is defined as a phenomenon encompassing different types of mentality (political, social, cultural).

It is worth noting that there are many similarities in the definitions of both mentality and the result of mentality. G.V. Akopov and T.V. Ivanova, who in their article "The phenomenon of mentality as a problem of consciousness" [5,23] associate mentality with the consciousness of a group of people in a certain period of time and in a given space. It is important to note that mentality consists in unconscious collective features that find their embodiment in both intangible and objectified forms of culture. Mentality, according to I.V. Konyreva, is a particular concept in relation to the general, or mentality. Therefore, we can talk about mentality on a local scale: the mentality of an individual or a social group, society or epoch.[6,2]

Being two different phenomena, mentality and conceptsphere interact with each other and influence each other. The mentality formed under the influence of objective social, cultural and political factors is the background for the conceptual sphere, or the field of knowledge and ideas of the people. However, the reverse movement is also possible: from the conceptual sphere to the mentality, when knowledge forms certain models and stereotypes in society. If the mentality is studied by methods of ethnopsychology and ethnoculturology, then the conceptsphere refers directly to the tasks of linguists and linguocognitologists, because the conceptsphere is "the sphere of thought, the information base of the cognitive consciousness of the people and the individual".

The conceptsphere is a complex system formation in which linguistic and cultural experience and part of the consciousness of the nation are recorded. In fiction, the conceptual sphere is, first of all, the assessments, judgments, ideas of the writer, his picture of the world. Researchers correlate the linguistic and cultural concept with mentality. The ethnospecific component of the concept occupies an important place in the content of the artistic concept. Values and valuations make up the concept layer. The correlation of cultural and artistic concepts is important in the study of not only the individual artistic world of the writer, but also the direction, style, current, epoch. With the help of linguocreative techniques, cultural concepts are reinterpreted and something of their own is selected from a huge layer of ideas and thoughts, correlating with the spirit of the time, in as a result, the concept becomes more individualized, personally specific.

The philosophy of the text reveals that "the modern text is busy "attributing" everything cultural the context, the entire sphere of conscious and unconscious language as an a priori condition of thinking, perception, experience. Language as an ontology of culture -an invention of the modern era" .

It was mentioned that the associative-semantic field is a way of presenting an artistic concept. In this regard, it would be logical to consider in more detail the theory of text associations, which is part of the direction of the communicative stylistics of a literary text. Intra-textual associations are very important for understanding the aesthetic and semantic aspects of the work. The analysis of associative fields is necessary for understanding the individual author's picture of the world. The associative field was considered in linguistic, psychological and psycholinguistic aspects in the works of L.S. Vygotsky, A. A. Leontiev, A. A. Zalevskaya, Y. N. Karaulov, A. P. Klimenko, L.Y. Maksimov, N. S. Bolotnova, etc. In this understanding the artistic worldview of a writer of English origin is important for comprehending the emotional and philosophical code that reveals the mentality and worldview of a certain group of people.

The peculiarity of the associative field in a work of fiction is the combination of words that at first glance have nothing in common. The dominant of the field are keywords with conceptual significance. N.S. Bolotnova suggests the following methodology for analyzing the associative layer of the concept in fiction:

1. Identification of the out-of-text associative potential of a keyword.
2. On the basis of the formed associative field, determine the main directions of association.
3. Analysis of the regulatory means of the text and determination of their associative relationship by adjacency, similarity or contrast.
4. Identification of associative series of text associates and directions of association.
5. Formation of the associative field and definition of the content of the concept .

According to D. Lakoff, cognitive models are the mental representations of the concept, but in fact we are talking about cognitive structures that can be used in cognitive poetics to explain the emergence of individual author meanings.

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